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Emphasizing peer learning in a virtually flipped classroom

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ABSTRACT

Peer learning is a powerful learning resource used in many ways in modern education. At Aalborg University it plays an important part of the PBL concept used since 1974, most important in the Problem based Projects solved in groups, but also in courses where lectures is supported by assignments in groups facilitated by teachers.

Aalborg University also offers online part-time master programmes using the PBL principles transformed to online environments where face to interface replaces face to face and courses uses flipped lecture formats instead of transmission based lectures.

Participants in these programmes are often very motivated and they follow the flipped instructions and read the suggested material, but do they also use their study group and experience peer learning?

This question is investigated in this paper using one semester in the 2-year part-time programme: Master in Problem Based Learning in Engineering and Science.

Questions and assignments uploaded by participants is used to analyse the activity from the participants together with recordings from online sessions where teachers answer uploaded questions and calls for discussion with the participants. Questionnaires is used to collect data about how much the study groups are used and if peer learning happens.

Conference Key Areas: Curriculum Development, Open and Online Engineering Education, Engineering Education Research

Keywords: Peer Learning, online education, lifelong learning

INTRODUCTION

Aalborg UNESCO Centre for Problem Based Learning in Engineering Science and Sustainability offers a Master in Problem Based Learning in Engineering and Science programme (MPBL) [1].

It is a 2-year part-time online programme, equivalent to a one-year full-time study (60 ECTS credits), targeting faculty staff at institutions, which want to change to PBL, or faculty staff who are interested in learning more about PBL.

A driving force for the Aalborg Centre is the exemplary practice Aalborg University has for both PBL and integration of sustainability in engineering and science education.

Since 1974, Aalborg University has practiced PBL as the pedagogical learning methodology during the entire study period [2].

The MPBL programme is designed according to the PBL principles used at Aalborg University, being problem based and project organized. The participants work in teams with educational experiments designed to solve real-life educational problems, preferable located within their own teaching practice.

The programme is based on a combination of academic, problem-oriented and interdisciplinary approaches to teaching and learning. Teaching formats include but may not be limited to the following methods [3]:

- On-line lectures
- Web mediated project work
- On-line workshops
- Self-study and readings
- Web mediated exercises (individually and in groups)
- Facilitation feedback
- Self- and group reflection
- Individual portfolio work

This is a new version of the MPBL programme, refined from a previous programme that was running for the very first time more than 10 years ago, with the first batch of participants getting their degree at the SEFI conference in Aalborg 2008.

Starting up the new version in autumn 2014 the teaching staff was more experienced with online education and the courses was planned to use ideas from flipped learning. Both the participants and the teaching staff was very satisfied with the new version of the programme and claimed to have learned very much and gained a lot of knowledge from the discussions and interactions with the other participants and the involved educators.

It is well known that peer learning is an important learning resource in the PBL setting at Aalborg University [4] but it is not yet investigated if learning in the online MPBL programme is mostly individual or to what extent peer learning is used.

This paper investigates this issue, studying the second run of the new MPBL programme, starting in September 2016.

1 MPBL PROGRAMME

This section will explain the outline of the Master of Problem Based Learning programme.

1.1 Overview

The outline of the MPBL programme is shown in *Table 1*.

Table 1. MPBL programme [3]

Master in Problem Based Learning in Engineering and Science (MPBL)				
Course/Project	Exam form	Assessment	Grading	ECTS
Semester 1: Development of teaching competences (15 ECTS)				
Project: Teaching portfolio	Written	Internal	7 step scale	5
Course 1: Teaching and learning theories	Oral	Internal	Pass/fail	5
Course 2: Collaborative learning skills and scientific writing	Oral/written	Internal	Pass/fail	5

Semester 2: PBL models and principles (15 ECTS)				
Project: : Design and planning of a PBL semester	Oral	Internal	7 step scale	5
Course 1: PBL models and curriculum development	Written	Internal	7 step scale	5
Course 2: Facilitation skills and teaching methods for active learning	Oral/written	Internal	Pass/fail	5
Semester 3: Management of change and evaluation (15 ECTS)				
Project: Implementation of change	Oral	External	7 step scale	5
Course 1: Management of change to PBL	Written	Internal	7 step scale	5
Course 2: Research methods for educational evaluation	Oral/written	Internal	Pass/fail	5
Semester 4: Master's thesis project (15 ECTS)				
Project: Master's thesis	Oral	External	7 step scale	15
ECTS Total				60

The MPBL programme is a problem based learning programme, exemplary for its own contents and delivered as online distance education. A semester in the MPBL programme includes a problem based project and two courses, the main study activity being the project. *Figure 1* depicts the project as a boundary object for all other learning activities. In the project theory meets practice [1, study form].

Figure 1: The project is at the core in the MPBL programme [1, study form].

Learning activities supporting the project are: Facilitation; readings; discussions; peer learning; reflections; courses etc.

Each course have 5 sessions, each with a written instruction with readings and facilitating questions to be discusses in study groups of 2 or 3 persons. The participants can then poste questions and there is an online session where the teacher both answer the posted questions and opens for discussion and experience exchange with and among the participants.

1.2 Focus

Investigating the whole MPBL programme will take more than two years and require substantial resources. At this moment it is possible to look at the ongoing semester 2: PBL models and principles (15 ECTS). The semester consists of two online courses

and a project, see *Table 1*. Focus for the investigation is peer learning, both in the teams and amongst the different teams during on-line sessions in the courses.

The project will not be finalised until after deadline of this paper, so it will not be a part of this study, but might be subject for further studies.

Course 1: PBL models and curriculum development, is a theoretical course, and the online sessions are intended for answering the posted questions and inviting for discussions. This can be supplemented by “lecturing” about details in the subject of the session.

Course 2: Facilitation skills and teaching methods for active learning, is a more practical (hands on) course, with focus on sharing of experiences amongst the participants. This is emphasized in the facilitating questions and small assignments for the study groups before the online session. Each session is then used to discuss the different answers to both questions and assignments in order to provide good possibilities for peer learning across the study groups.

2 METHOD

The 2nd semester has 8 participants working in 3 teams as study groups in the courses, discussing literature and facilitating questions and working together on eventual assignments before online sessions. All of the participants are motivated in improving their teaching and have already made several attempts to do that.

Both the answers to assignments, discussions and questions posted for discussion in each session is available on the semester page and is used for analyzing the input from the participants before the online sessions.

All the online sessions is recorded, making it possible to analyze how much the participants are active in discussions and sharing experiences.

Questionnaires, see *Tabel 2*, is used to investigate differences in learning possibilities and outcome in the two courses: how this is perceived by the participants and how they have used peer learning.

Tabel 2. Questions for each session as example

Did you use your study group for: (mark with a X)	No (0)	A Little (1)	Medium (2)	A Lot (3)
Discussing and understanding of the suggested readings				
Discussion of the facilitating questions				
Posting questions for the lecturer				
Doing the assignment				
Did you learn something from each other? (peer learning)				

Comments: _____

How will you assess the on-line session: (mark with a X)	No (0)	A Little(1)	Medium(2)	A Lot (3)
It was about answering the posted questions				
It was a lecture				
It was a discussion forum sharing knowledge and experiences				

What did you like the best of the on-line session: _____

Why: _____

3 RESULTS

The results will be presented separately for each of the courses.

3.1 Course 1: PBL models and curriculum development

This is a theoretical course. The titles of the 5 sessions are:

1. PBL as an educational philosophy / PBL models
2. Curriculum Theories and Models
3. Field research and educational experiments
4. Assessment of learning outcomes within a PBL context
5. Project proposals to trigger the learning process

Analyses of posted questions and assignments

The first session is an introduction to PBL and the participants posted 5 questions that was answered by the teacher at the online session.

For session 2 there were only one question and zero for session 3 and 4. These three sessions was by far the most theoretical sessions and the teachers had to prepare slides for the online sessions based on what they thought would be interesting for the participants as supplement to the readings because there was no questions to answer.

The last session was a hands-on session with an assignment to make a project proposal in the study groups and present it at the online session. Two of the study groups made the assignment and presented it but due to misunderstandings the third group did not collaborate on the assignment and only one of the members uploaded an assignment. No questions was posted.

Analyses of recordings

Looking at the recordings from the online sessions it is clear that the teachers in the first 4 sessions had prepared many slides and used about 1 hour to explain the slides. The teachers was inviting the participants to comment and ask questions and the participants took the opportunity with app. half of them being active in each session. In the last session half an hour was used on presentation from the two groups that had answered the assignment. All of the group members took part in the presentation and other participants and the teacher was commenting and discussing the project proposals. The teacher had prepared a few slides based on the assignments and another half hour was used on presentation and discussion.

Analyses of questionnaires

The answers to the questionnaires reveals differences between the three study groups. The small group with 2 participants didn't use each other at all and didn't answer the questionnaire. The result from the other two groups is shown in *Table 3*.

Table 3. Results from questions about using the study group

Did you use your study group for: (mark with 0-3)	S 1	S 2	S 3	S 4	S 5
Discussing and understanding of the suggested readings	0-1	0-1	0-1	1-3	2-3
Discussion of the facilitating questions	1-2	0-1	0-1	0-1	2-3
Posting questions for the lecturer	1-2	0-1	0-1	0-1	2-3
Doing the assignment (only session 5 had group assignments)	0	0	0	0	2-3
Did you learn something from each other? (peer learning)	1-2	0-2	0-2	1-2	2-3

The results in *Table 3* shows that the activity in the study groups varies in the first 4 sessions and generally is marked at the lower end up to medium (2). In the last session

the study groups were asked to collaborate on the assignment raising the level to medium (2) to a lot (3) in all questions.

The answers to the questions concerning the online sessions is shown in *Table 4* that like *Table 3* shows differences in the marking of the first 4 (theoretical) sessions and the last (hands-on) session. The last session is assessed higher than the others regarding answering the posted questions and sharing knowledge and experiences, and lower (No) in being a lecture.

Table 4. Results from questions about assessing the online sessions

How will you assess the on-line session: (mark with 0-3)	S 1	S 2	S 3	S 4	S 5
It was about answering the posted questions	2	0-1	0-1	0-1	3
It was a lecture	1-2	1-2	1-2	1-2	0
It was a discussion forum sharing knowledge and experiences	2	0-2	0-2	0-2	1-2

One of the participants had a general comment to the 2 last questions in *Table 2* for the 3 first sessions. What do you like the best about the online session: “The presentation and discussion forum”, Why: “The experience of the professor”.

In the last session the comments from the same participant was: What do you like the best about the online session: “The presentation of each group”, Why: “I liked the activity”.

These quotes indicate that in the theoretical sessions the experienced professor is important for the presentations and discussions, and when the participants is asked to use their own experience it is also highly valued as a learning resource.

3.1 Course 2: Facilitation skills and teaching methods for active learning

This is a practical (hands on) course. The titles of the 5 sessions are:

1. Reflection on teaching
2. Active learning – small class delivery
3. Active learning - in large and flipped classrooms
4. Facilitation roles
5. Facilitation skills - Maastricht tutoring

Analyses of posted questions and assignments

For the first 3 sessions 4 questions were posted and zero questions for the last 2 sessions. All of the sessions except session 5 used facilitating questions addressing the participant’s experiences as a teacher, to be discussed in the study groups and in session 1 and 2 this was supported by individual assignments on the same subject, and in session 4 there was a group based assignment.

The answers to the assignments was uploaded to the semester page, so everyone could read each other’s experiences. Most of the participants uploaded the assignments.

Analyses of recordings

The online sessions was prepared based on the questions and the answers to the assignments, that were often very usable to identify subjects for discussions. Like in course 1 the teacher used some time presenting the different slides, and called for comments and questions. The last part took up more time than in course 1 and there were more people participating actively.

Listening to the recordings it is very clear that all of the participants are experienced teachers and uses their knowledge and experience in the discussions.

Analyses of questionnaires

The answers to the questionnaires reveals the same differences between the three study groups as in course 1. The small group with 2 participants didn't use each other at all and only one answered the questionnaire. These answers is only used in *Table 6*, so only the result from the other two groups is shown in *Table 5*.

Table 5. Results from questions about using the study group

Did you use your study group for: (mark with 0-3)	S 1	S 2	S 3	S 4	S 5
Discussing and understanding of the suggested readings	2	2	0-1	0-2	0
Discussion of the facilitating questions	2	2	0-1	1-2	0
Posting questions for the lecturer	1-2	1-2	0	0-1	0
Doing the assignment (only session 5 had group assignments)	0	0	0	1-2	0
Did you learn something from each other? (peer learning)	2-3	1-2	0-1	1-2	0

The results in *Table 5* shows that the activity in the study groups is highest in the first 2 sessions. The last session had no readings and facilitating questions, so the study groups had no reason to collaborate. Peer learning was marked highest in session 1, where there was an individual assignment about teaching experiences that was uploaded for sharing with all participants.

The answers to the questions concerning the online sessions is shown in *Table 6* that shows higher marks for answering posted questions in the first 4 sessions than in course 1 (*Table 4*), probably because more questions was posted. The same 4 sessions was also marked lower as a lecture and app. the same as sharing knowledge and experiences. The last session is assessed low like in *Table 5*.

Table 6. Results from questions about assessing the online sessions

How will you assess the on-line session: (mark with 0-3)	S 1	S 2	S 3	S 4	S 5
It was about answering the posted questions	2-3	2-3	1-3	1-3	0-1
It was a lecture	0-1	0-1	0	0-2	0
It was a discussion forum sharing knowledge and experiences	1-2	1-2	1-2	1-2	0

There were similar comments to the first session about liking the activity and presentation done by the participants in the online session, as to the last session in course 1, and similar to session 1 to 3 in course 1 the professor's role was highlighted in session 4.

An interesting quote from session 2: What do you like the best about the online session: "The online session were based on feedback from the previous work done by each of us". This indicates that using the answers to assignments to highlight subject in the online sessions is highly valued.

4 DISCUSSION

The two courses investigated is the second semester of the MPBL education so the participants are familiar with the setup using instructions with facilitating questions and readings.

The results shows that the participants are motivated and experienced teachers that follow the instructions and do the readings. They do not post many questions for the online sessions, but the recordings shows that at least half of them are active in the discussions and participate on a level showing that they have studied the material. The number of both posted questions and active participants in the discussions was generally higher in course 2 (hands-on) than in course 1 (theoretical).

During the first 4 sessions in course 1 the active groups used each other mostly below medium, but the group assignment in session 5 called for more collaboration and improved the peer learning in the study groups.

In course 2 the activity and collaboration was a little higher in the first 4 sessions and very low in the last session being without the usual readings and facilitating questions.

As an average, the participants reported peer learning to happen at a level of 1,5 (between a little and medium) with session 5 in course 1 and session 1 in course 2 being the best rated at 2,5 (between medium and a lot). These two sessions was the most hands-on sessions, using the participants experience as teachers in the facilitating questions and the assignments to promote collaboration, experience exchange and peer learning.

5 CONCLUSION

This paper set out to investigate the use of peer learning in the second semester of a Master in Problem Based Learning Programme. Two courses was the focus, one being theoretical the other more practical (hands-on).

The participants was not very active to discuss the readings and facilitating questions in the beginning, and it took 3 sessions before they realized the potential and started using the study groups more actively. A group based assignment in session 5 of the first course promoted the collaboration and peer learning.

The second and more practical course called for exchanging of teaching experiences, using the facilitating questions and assignments in 4 sessions to set up the best possibilities for that. The outcome was more activity, both in the study groups and the online sessions.

In this investigation, it was possible to develop and use peer learning in online education, but the teachers had to promote it and the participants took a while to adjust to it. Assignments enhanced peer learning and it came easier in hands-on sessions where the participants own experience was used actively.

The Curriculum for the MPBL program is going to be updated during the next year and the results from this investigation will be used to make changes promoting peer learning. Plans for following up research on the coming MPBL educations will be made as a part of the updating procedure.

REFERENCES

- [1] Homepage of Aalborg UNESCO Centre for Problem Based Learning in Engineering Science and Sustainability, MPBL education: <http://www.mpbl.aau.dk/> (9.7.2017)
- [2] Barge, Scott: Principles of Problem and Project Based Learning – The Aalborg PBL Model, Aalborg University 2010, p.5.
- [3] Curriculum for Master in Problem Based Learning in Engineering and Science: http://www.mpbl.aau.dk/digitalAssets/83/83350_77885_study-regulation-mpbl-28-08-2013.pdf
- [4] Jensen, L. P. & Mosgaard, M. (2016), Collaboration and Peer Learning in Problem Based Learning, SEFI annual conference proceedings: Engineering Education on Top of the World: Industry University Cooperation. SEFI: European Association for Engineering Education, 9 p.